

Composer as Constrainer in Model-Led Piano Sheet Music Generation

Simon Colton, Louis Bradshaw, Berker Banar, Keshav Bhandari and Marikaiti Primenta

School of Electronic Engineering and Computer Science

Queen Mary University of London

United Kingdom

s.colton@qmul.ac.uk

Abstract

We describe a generative music system designed to produce expressive MIDI music transcribed into scores for the piano. The approach entails the constrained application of a transformer neural model which generates expressive MIDI music. The constraints enable an interpretation of the transformer’s output tokens so that they can be captured as notes on sheet music. Additional functionality affords more control over the form, difficulty and playability of the music, enabling composers to direct the music generation by specifying a series of constraints. Producing the best results requires a model-led approach whereby the notes the transformer produces solves a constraint satisfaction problem (CSP), but the nature of the solution also dictates which CSP to solve next. We assess progress via feedback from two pianists about nine generated pieces, in terms of expressivity, quality, likeability and playability of the sheet music, and show that the pieces are in general well-received.

1 Introduction

We are interested in producing expressive MIDI music for the piano, accompanied by sheet music which captures the essence of the music in written form as a PDF file. Our aim is for the sheet music to be *playable* in the sense that the score is not just a literal transcription of the MIDI performance capturing all the expressive details, but rather a simpler rationalisation which can be interpreted by pianists at a later date. One way to achieve this would be to produce expressive MIDI files and then use an approach which converts MIDI to MusicXML, which can then be converted to a score. Such functionality is available in commercial software such as GarageBand and MuseScore and is an active area of research, with recent state of the art approaches described in (Liu et al., 2022) and (Beyer and Dai, 2024). Unfortunately, MIDI to score conversion is not a solved problem and we highlight some of the limitations in an exercise in appendix 1.

After some initial experimentation, we found that converting expressive MIDI to piano scores usually produces quite unreadable/unplayable sheet music. For this reason, we implemented a technique which largely bypasses this conversion stage. In particular, our approach generates MIDI piano music with expressive dynamic and tempo changes including rubato, accelerando and rallentando, but does so in a constrained way which enables the tagging of each MIDI onset with a particular beat and bar number. This makes the MIDI to MusicXML conversion process straightforward and produces readable/playable sheet music. In essence, our approach is akin to asking a piano improviser to play in a more (but not aggressively) quantised manner, to make it easier to transcribe their creations, while not noticeably reducing the quality, diversity or expressivity of the music. In section 2, we describe the TTM transformer model underpinning this approach – acting as the improviser in the above analogy – and in section 3, we describe the constraint system wrapped around this to allow the neurosymbolic production of expressive MIDI music accompanied by playable sheet music. As further described in section 3, we enhanced the constraint approach to allow user control over the form, structure, physical playability and difficulty of the music generated.

We focus here on describing the system and how it can be used to create piano music in a controlled way, with a composer imposing constraints which dictate changes in dynamics and tempo over certain bar ranges, accompaniment styles, key signatures, scales and other elements of the music, with the transformer filling in the details. While there is still more work to be done, we are at the stage where the outputs from the system can be evaluated. To help shape future developments and evaluations, we undertook a pilot study with two pianists/piano teachers assessing the value (for pianists and students) of both the sheet music and the expressive renditions, as described in section 4. We end by discussing some recent related work on sheet music generation in section 5 and by describing our plans for future work in section 6.

2 The TTM Token Prediction Transformer

We have trained a transformer neural model which we call The Transformer Model (TTM) here for the purposes of anonymisation. As described in (Vaswani et al., 2017), transformers are a well-studied and successful generative model for the production of token sequences, which are at the heart of many large language models. The training set for TTM was around 1.2 million MIDI files produced via automatic transcription to MIDI of expressive human performances of piano music in YouTube videos. The transcription process and the compilation and evaluation of the open-source dataset is described in (Bradshaw and Colton, 2025). Given an input musical prompt expressed as MIDI onset, pitch, volume and duration tokens, TTM works by predicting the next token in a sequence, building up tokens for the MIDI music in a note-by-note fashion. In a paper under review, we demonstrate with a listening study that, when extending given musical prompts, outputs from TTM are better received than from state of the art MIDI generators in terms of the quality of the music, and are competitive with outputs from commercial audio generation systems like Suno (suno.com).

In the application described here, we use TTM in an *ab-initio* way, i.e., with no musical prompt given. Given the expressive nature of the training set, the music that TTM outputs is likewise expressive, with crescendo and diminuendo passages, grace notes, accented notes, trills, glissandos, expressive phrasing and dynamic timings all audible, but not represented explicitly in the output. It is the expressive timing elements of the output music that cause the main difficulty in converting TTM’s output to sheet music via MIDI to score convertors like (Liu et al., 2022) and (Beyer and Dai, 2024). In particular, the music contains moments of *rubato* which apply strategic pausing to certain notes, as well as *accelerando* and *rallentando* passages, where the music speeds up and slows respectively. TTM’s output also simulates the use of a piano’s sustain pedal and the reverb acoustics of the room in which the piano was played. In practice, this all means that the MIDI durations for the notes TTM produces are highly unreliable indicators of suitable on-sheet note durations. In appendix 1, we show that MIDI to score convertors produce outputs that are not yet as readable/playable as would be expected in sheet music.

We render the output MIDI pieces from TTM into audio using a piano SoundFont (Micha, 2023), and the results sound sufficiently like real piano recordings from human pianists. We are interested in producing sheet music so that pianists can actually play the pieces on a piano. In this context, the expressive quality of the music that TTM produces is very valuable, as it indicates how the sheet music could be played. This may help people to more appreciate the music in the sense of explainable computational creativity (Llano et al., 2020). As described in the next section, to produce playable sheet music capturing TTM’s expressive MIDI performances, we chose to carefully wrap a system around TTM which constrains its output to be more amenable to transcription onto a score. We were able to extend the constraining system so that composers can control certain aspects of the music, while still taking advantage of the creative power of TTM to produce diverse music of acceptable quality within the constraints.

3 Neurosymbolic Sheet Music Generation

Our approach brings together generative deep learning (Foster, 2023) and constraint solving (Rossi, van Beek, and Walsh, 2006) in a neurosymbolic manner (Bhuyan et al., 2024). In overview, a constraint satisfaction problem (CSP) consists of a number of variables which each have a domain of values which they can be assigned. Solving a CSP involves simultaneously assigning values to all variables in such a way that a given set of *constraints* are all upheld. Sometimes a CSP can be quite loose with many solutions to it, and CSPs can be made more flexible by splitting the constraints

into *hard* constraints which must be satisfied in any solution, and *soft* constraints which need not be satisfied (Schiex, 1992). CSP solving techniques tend to narrow down the domain of variables while upholding the constraints until no further narrowing is possible. If a variable’s domain has dwindled to nothing, then backtracking must occur, but if one or more values remain for each variable, then a solution can be chosen randomly from these possibilities for each variable. This provides an opportunity for more intelligent choosing of values from the constrained possibilities. In particular, a neural model could be used to choose between the remaining values, by predicting which is the best in a particular context.

We frame the problem of generating sheet music for the piano as producing a series of CSPs to be solved, the solutions of which dictate the onset, pitch, volume and duration of a musical note. Whenever the constraints allow multiple solutions, we employ TTM to intelligently choose between them. This involves next-token prediction using a process of disabling certain logits before sampling, as described below. We have enabled *constraint-led* generation, where constraints are applied in a given sequence to produce music with a particular form and structure. However, this can be relaxed to admit more model-led aspects, by loosening constraints and using the solution that TTM chooses for a CSP to dictate the nature of the next CSP to solve. This hands over more creative responsibility to the model, potentially producing more interesting, surprising and higher quality music.

To make progress, we made the following simplifying assumptions:

- Outputs can be captured in 4/4 time, with no changes in time signature.
 - A suitable key signature can be chosen post-generation by finding the one which minimises accidentals played during the music, with no key signature changes required.
 - Notes can be separated into two groupings, one for the left hand and one for the right hand, with no overlapping of hands on the keyboard required.
 - Notes played simultaneously in a chord in either hand all have the same on-sheet duration and audible duration, although these don’t have to match.
 - Notes or chords which follow sequentially (in time) are delimiters for those before it. In particular, the onset of a note dictates the on-sheet duration of any notes immediately preceding it.
 - On-sheet note durations can be limited to a range of one-eighth of a beat (semiquaver) to four beats (semibreve), with tied notes extending this to as much as eight beats.
-

We plan to relax these assumptions in future work, as it is clear that the unconstrained music generated by TTM doesn’t precisely conform to these limitations. For instance, it often produces waltz-like music which should be captured in 3/4 time. However, in practice with constraining applied, we’ve found that there is a good correlation between TTM’s expressive performances and the sheet music capturing them, despite these limitations. We evaluate this claim in section 4 below.

3.1 Logit Mackling and Quantising Within Ranges

TTM produces a token in two stages. Firstly, it passes the input sequence (i.e., the tokens generated so far) through the model to produce *logits* from its final layer, as a vector of floats. Secondly, via a softmax transform, the logits are interpreted as a probability distribution and sampled to choose a single logit, the position of which dictates the token output by the model. This provides an opportunity to intervene after the first stage and effectively reduce to zero the likelihood of a particular set of logits being output, hence restricting the tokens produced (and in turn, the notes generated). This is achieved by simply setting the logits at certain positions to minus infinity. Lacking a name for this process from the literature, we call it *logit mackling*, as in some English dialects *mackling* means fixing something in a makeshift manner.

Logit mackling effectively specifies a CSP which is solved by TTM choosing amongst the possibilities remaining after constraining, to best fit the sequence of tokens it has already produced. We describe below numerous constraint types which effectively rule-out certain tokens at certain times, according to the requirements of a user. The first type are quantisation constraints, which enforce onsets to start within intervals of milliseconds after the previous onset. This affords an interpretation of the notes as starting on particular fractions of beats in a bar, with the smallest fraction being 1/4 of a beat. This

markedly reduces the requirement of dotted, double dotted and tied notes, which produces rather messy, unreadable scores like those in appendix 1.

Constraining notes to start on a quarter of a beat means that the music is far easier to read, yet can still have up to sixteen notes of melody per bar. However, we found that strict constraining of the onset tokens so that notes start on exactly the semiquaver marks produced highly-quantised music which was mechanical sounding rather than expressive. For this reason, we instead constrain the onset tokens relative to the onset of the most recently generated note in the appropriate left-hand or right-hand set. The onset tokens allowed are in ranges of milliseconds since the previous onset, with the ranges non-overlapping. This loosening of the constraints means that TTM is able to choose note onsets earlier or later than the user-specified beats per minute (BPM) would suggest, and hence can express *accelerando*/*rallentando* passages and the use of *rubato*.

As an example, if the user has specified an *allegro* BPM of 120, this means that each beat lasts 0.5 seconds, and each quarter beat should be $0.125s = 125ms$. In this case, the duration between semiquaver onsets is constrained to be between $0.125 * 0.5$ and $0.125 * 1.5$ milliseconds, i.e., in the range from 62.5ms to 187.5ms. In practice, TTM's tokens are calibrated in 10ms intervals, so it would be able to choose between tokens in the set $\{60, 70, \dots, 180\}$ for the audible duration between on-sheet semiquavers. This gives ample room for expressivity, but does not lead to an impression that a semiquaver should have been a (shorter) demisemiquaver or a (longer) quaver on the score.

3.2 Comparison Study

By constraining the onsets to occur within certain ranges since the previous onsets, with the ranges representing on-sheet durations like semiquavers, it is possible to tag each onset with a specific bar and beat, using the simplifying assumptions given above. This enables a much easier transcription to MusicXML and via MuseScore to a PDF score. We informally found that the constraining process didn't compromise the quality, diversity or expressivity of the output. However, working in an *ab-initio* fashion, TTM is not particularly robust, and wrong formulations which inappropriately constrain tokens at the start can be compounded through auto-completion, producing low quality music. Hence, a concern throughout the project has been that mackling the logits of TTM's outputs would ruin either the sophistication of the compositions or the expressivity of the performances.

To put this to the test, we asked three participants – all with extensive knowledge of TTM and its outputs – to determine whether a TTM output was from a quantisation-constrained or unconstrained generation, using only audio to decide. Twenty samples each from an unconstrained and a constrained generation were provided and participants determined which they came from, or stated that they could not decide. We found that the participants couldn't confidently tell whether a constrained process was used or not, and, on average, they were only able to categorise 32% of the samples correctly, i.e., less than would be achieved by random allocation. Hence, it seems unlikely that the quantisation constraining is audibly affecting the quality of the music.

3.3 Model-Led Application of Hard and Soft Onset Constraints

Having addressed the problem of producing music which can be transcribed to a score, we extended the constraining approach to give composers more control over the generative process and hence the nature of the music produced. Users can specify a set of *hard onset constraints* as a specific number of notes that must be played at specific quarter beats in the music. Each hard onset constraint for a segment of music has associated constraints on the pitches, volumes and (audible) durations of the MIDI notes played at that onset. This is done in a per-segment way, where a segment could be two beats, or a four-beat bar, etc. The constraints for a segment are applied repeatedly as the music progresses, up to a user-specified number of seconds, beats or bars. At this point, the next user-specified segment is chosen for application, or the generation stops if there are none left.

Using these basic constraints, we produced simple music such as the 3 four-bar pieces presented on the left of figure 1. Here, the hard onset constraints for the right hand (RH) melody dictated exactly one note be played on each half-beat of the bar, producing quavers on the score. The hard onset constraints for the left hand (LH) dictated a chord of exactly three notes on the first beat of each bar. RH pitches were constrained at or above middle C, and LH pitches between low C and middle C. No other constraints were specified. While there are issues with them (see below), they do demonstrate how the loose constraints can be solved in quite different ways by TTM. In particular, the first and

Figure 1: Left: example pieces generated with hard onset constraints only. Right: example pieces generated with the CDG given in the text. In the performance MIDI for these pieces, red/green notes are held for longer/shorter than the average over all the notes of the same on-sheet duration.

```

CDG: SS1(1 bar) -> SS2(2 bars) -> SS3(1 bar)
SS1: NC1,NC2, SS2: NC1,NC3, SS3: NC1,NC4
NC1 (LH): p=(48, 59) v=(30, 80) d=(10, 5000)
h=[(b1.0, n=3)] s=[(b2.0, n=3)]
NC2 (RH): p=(60, 98) v=(50, 120) d=(10, 5000)
h=[(b1.0, n=1)] s=[(b1.5 to b4.5, n=1)]
NC3 (RH): p=(60, 98) v=(50, 120) d=(10, 5000)
h=[] s=[(b1.0 to b4.75, n=2)]
NC4 (RH): p=(60, 98) v=(50, 120) d=(10, 5000)
h=[(b1.0, n=3)] s=[]

```

Figure 2: Example CDG with 3 segment specifications (SS) of note constraints (NC). (h)ard and (s)oft onsets given as pairs of (b)eat and (n)umber allowed on the beat. Also given are the (p)itch, (v)olume and (d)uration constraint ranges, and whether left (LH) or right (RH) hands play the generated notes.

third pieces are more classical and relatively easy-listening, while the second piece – with more discordance – is more challenging and dystopian. By comparing the on-sheet note durations with the audible (MIDI) durations played, we have colour-coded the notes, so that green indicates notes played for 5% less than average and red indicates notes played for 5% more than average. While these short pieces don't really afford much expressive rendering, the colouring highlights that TTM does not choose perfectly quantised note durations.

If the note onsets in a generated piece are the same for each bar, the composition may seem overly regular or predictable. This might be fine for a technical exercise like those in (Hanon, 1993), where pianists practice repetitive music. However, we wanted to explore giving TTM creative license to invent rhythms by choosing which quarter beat onsets in a segment can have between 0 and a user-given maximum number of notes starting on them. In order to describe the way in which hard and soft constraints are applied during the generation of a piece, in appendix 2 we present a series of definitions and an algorithmic breakdown of the process. This involves the user specifying a *constraint decision graph* (CDG) which specifies how the hard and soft onset constraints change as the generation of the music progresses.

A key observation we have made is that TTM should be used as a decision procedure as well as a token predictor, i.e., it should make decisions about the direction of the music via the generation of a token which might not be used for the music itself. In particular, with only soft constraints to satisfy, TTM may prescribe no notes at these onsets. However, if given only the choice of a note on a soft onset or one on the next hard onset, it may add a soft onset note. We found that this led to artefacts, i.e., notes at the end of segments which seemed superfluous. This led to poor quality music, so we implemented a way by which – when there are only soft constraints left to fulfill before the next hard constraint – TTM has the option of choosing an onset token after the end of the last soft onset, which does not satisfy the constraints for the composition. If this choice is taken, TTM has essentially decided to add no soft onset notes from the options remaining. In this case, as there have been tokens generated that are no longer required, the system *backtracks* and resets the KV cache (Liu et al., 2024) of TTM. This process is captured by the *overflow* function in Algorithm 1 in appendix 2, which appends a range of two seconds of onsets to those allowed by the soft constraints.

Importantly, the approach has been designed to give TTM the most options in solving each CSP, as each time we have removed a restriction on the logits which was not needed, we have found that TTM produces better music. As an example, while notes must be added in onset order, Algorithm 1 ensures that no specific ordering on chord notes is required, e.g., from lowest to highest pitch. When TTM was trained, the order of simultaneous notes was randomised, so TTM has not learned to generate chord notes in a fixed order. Hence, to get the best out of TTM, we needed to ensure it can add chord notes in any order, as per Algorithm 1.

On the right of figure 1, we present 3 four-bar pieces generated using the same constraint decision graph (CDG) with both hard and soft onset constraints. As portrayed in figure 2, the CDG has three segments and transitions from one to the next occur after bar 1 and bar 3. The onsets for the RH melody are relaxed from bar 1 to 2, with quavers only in the first bar and semiquavers allowed in bars 2 and 3. The final segment ensures each piece finishes with a chord in the right hand. Soft constraints empower flexibility in the notes TTM chooses to satisfy the constraints and the three pieces are quite different. For instance, the soft onsets in the right hand can be ignored completely, so that simple, slower pieces such as the third one are possible, as well as more involved pieces such as the first two.

3.4 Additional Constraints

By analysing the music, our system assigns a key signature requiring fewest accidentals on the score. In future, we plan to use key detection models to help assign the key signature. The system also adds appropriate dynamic and pedal markings, along with crescendo, diminuendo, accelerando and rallentando markings. In the music of figure 1, some of the pieces would be very difficult, if not impossible, to play due to physical limitations of players' hands. To help address such issues, and to give more control to users, we implemented three additional constraint types as follows.

- **Cluster Constraints.** The system can gather and analyse notes already in the music to derive extra constraints on the onset, pitch and duration of the note to generate next. Focusing on pitch ranges, this has enabled us to force (a) chord sequences or chord limitations, such as major or minor only, or that the chord should span only 12 semitones on the keyboard, making it likely playable, and (b) interval sequences or interval limitations, for instance forcing arpeggios.
- **Drift Constraints.** The system can dynamically alter constraints as the music progresses. This enables the user to specify where a crescendo or diminuendo should start, how long it should last and how much the average volume of the notes should increase/decrease by. Likewise, by specifying a drift constraint on the BPM used to set the onsets in a segment, the user can specify accelerando and rallentando passages. By applying a drift constraint to pitches, the user can specify that the notes should move in a particular direction on the piano keyboard.
- **Global Constraints.** The user specifies the beats per minute and number of bars (or seconds) that generated pieces should last. If desired, they can also specify a scale for the pitches of the notes to be constrained to, including major and minor scales but also more exotic ones such as Hungarian minor or Persian (Hut and Anderson, 1974). Global constraints can be changed at strategic places, so users can impose a change to the scale, and/or a change in tempo, by changing the BPM used to determine onset constraints.

4 An Evaluation Pilot Study

The developer of the system described here is a pianist and amateur composer who specified three constraint decision graphs using a user interface within a Colab notebook for the system.¹ Details of the CDGs for the *Feelz*, *Alberti Bass* and *Freeform* series of compositions the composer specified and an example composition for each type are given in appendix 3. In addition, video performances – consisting of an expressive audio rendering with an animated score – for three of each type of composition are provided in the supplementary material. These nine compositions were chosen in a relatively realistic cherry-picking exercise, where 3 for each type were chosen from 20 outputs.

To gain feedback on the nine compositions, we asked two pianists to watch a video performance of each piece, study the PDF sheet music, and answer questions. Both pianists have passed grade 8 and

¹The notebook will be made publicly available for testing, if the paper is accepted.

Criteria	Alberti	Feelz	Freeform	Av.
Expressivity	3.00	3.67	4.00	3.56
Fidelity	3.00	3.33	4.00	3.44
Quality	3.33	3.83	2.17	3.11
Recommend	3.17	3.83	2.17	3.06
Playability	2.83	3.67	2.67	3.06
Video	3.00	3.50	3.00	3.17
Likeability	2.83	3.67	3.50	3.33
Practice	3.50			
Melancholic		4.00		
Appreciation	3.09	3.69	3.07	3.28

Table 1: Average scores from questions asked about 3 pieces from the three composition types. An overall appreciation score (out of four) is given as an average of the criteria scores.

one has gone further in gaining an ARSM diploma. Moreover, both are piano teachers as a secondary occupation. The questions probed their opinions about the quality, playability and likeability of each piece, whether the video performance for it matched the sheet music and was expressive and useful, and whether the pieces achieved the composer’s aims. Each question was multiple choice, with four answers, ranging from negative feedback about the music (scoring 1) to positive feedback (scoring 4).

The numerical averages from the questions are given in table 1. Participants were asked whether the performance video was expressive, i.e., sounding like a human player, to which they answered, on average between 3 (“Quite a lot, but not totally”) and 4 (“Definitely”). Asked about the performance fidelity, i.e., whether it matched the sheet music, the answers were also between 3 and 4. When asked whether the piece of music was of sufficient quality for a piano student to use it as part of their repertoire, the average answer was close to 3 (“Probably”). This was also the answer to a question about whether – as piano teachers – it would be appropriate to recommend this piece to a student. The average score for playability was given as around 3 (“Probably with a few edits”). When asked the question “Do you like this piece of music and can imagine mastering it and playing it for people” the average answer was between 3 and 4, but closer to “Probably” than “Yes”. Finally, when asked whether the video performance was helpful to determine how to play the piece, the average answer was around 3 (“Quite a lot, but not totally”). For the Alberti Bass pieces, participants were asked whether the sheet music provided good practice for the accompaniment style and arpeggios, and the average answer was between 3 (“Quite a lot, but could be improved”) and 4 (“Definitely”). For the Feelz pieces, when asked whether the music delivered a melancholic sound for an emotional impact, both participants answered “Definitely” for all compositions.

As per table 1, Feelz pieces were most highly appreciated overall, with a score of 3.69 out of 4. While there is still room for improvement, we find these results encouraging, and will use them in designing future evaluation experiments with a larger cohort of pianists. The participants also gave valuable qualitative feedback including ways to improve the sheet music, which we will use to direct future work. Criticisms included: places where the music would need editing to be playable; lack of phrasing evident in the performance or marked on the score; no indication of which melody notes should be brought out during a performance of a complex passage; lack of quality endings to pieces, in particular leaving tensions unresolved; lack of clarity around tempo and dynamic changes; occasional inappropriate cadences; unwelcome dissonances and repetitions; melodies in the wrong octave; and one hand drowning out the other. While participants were asked to concentrate on the negatives, some positive aspects of the music were given, including: realism in the performance, e.g., with expressive rubato; stimulating progression of the music, e.g., building of up tension and complexity; and beautiful phrasing of music passing between the hands.

5 Related Work

Various systems have been developed for sheet music generation. Some of these focus on lead sheet generation, e.g., (Makris, Agres, and Herremans, 2021) focuses on emotionally controlled lead sheet generation using a sequence-to-sequence framework that leverages both LSTM and transformer architectures. Similarly, (De Boom et al., 2020) employs LSTMs in a two-stage approach,

first generating harmonic and rhythmic templates and then layering a melody on top. (Pachet, Papadopoulos, and Roy, 2017) produced structured lead sheets by introducing variations in musical sequences. Moving beyond lead sheets, (Liu and Yang, 2018) generated 8-bar sheet music with multi-instrument arrangements, using conditional GANs. In contrast, (Acosta et al., 2022) explores image-domain solutions for sheet music generation, though outputs tend to have limited harmonic depth or musical coherence. MusicScore (Lin, Dai, and Kong, 2024) uses a UNet diffusion model (Yang et al., 2023) to generate sheet music that is both readable and playable, enabling text-based control over instrumentation and key signatures. Additionally, (Sakai, Segawa, and Kitahara, 2024) generates guitar sheet music in tablature notation from lead sheets, emphasizing playability through optimized guitar fretboard fingerings.

Generative approaches for music represented in ABC notation produce outputs amenable for transcription to scores, and projects such as FolkRNN (Sturm, Santos, and Korshunova, 2015) have taken advantage of this. Such approaches tend not to produce particularly expressive performances, so a separate process might be needed for that (Widmer and Goebel, 2004). A recent deep learning approach looks at musicality in ABC music generation and produces multiple types of sheet music with the NotaGen system (Wang et al., 2025). There have also been recent advances in modelling physical piano playing, with a dataset of fingerings (Nakamura, Saito, and Yoshii, 2020) and hand movements in piano playing (Gan et al., 2025), and work on a robotic piano player (Zakka et al., 2023). There have been many approaches to using constraint solving in music generation, with a survey in (Anders and Miranda, 2011). Similar to our approach, Pachet, Roy, and Barbieri (2011) pioneered a process of combining generative processes such as Hidden Markov Models (HMMs) with constraint solving. Other approaches combining HMMs and constraints have been investigated, e.g., to produce harmonic progressions (Eigenfeldt and Pasquier, 2010). Finally, sheet music seems set to become a more prominent target for generative deep learning, with large MusicXML (Long et al., 2024) and image datasets (Lin, Dai, and Kong, 2024) becoming available recently.

6 Conclusions and Future Work

We have wrapped a constraint system around a state of the art transformer model, to produce not just expressive MIDI music, but also playable sheet music, samples of which were well received by two experienced pianists. This is an active divergence (Broad et al., 2021) from how transformers are normally used and it has been difficult to separate logistics in the constraint system from musicality exhibited by TTM. A key lesson has been that TTM has broad and extensive knowledge of all aspects of piano music, but is only able to express this understanding via the repeated choosing of a single token from a dictionary. For this reason, to get the best out of TTM, we built the constraint system to not just guide the model, but to help interpret the decisions it makes. While we acknowledge there are some issues in the quality of the music produced, we now have in place a framework for neurosymbolic sheet music generation that can begin to address these issues.

We plan to investigate other neurosymbolic ways to transform logits before sampling, such as *logit nudging* which raises or lowers the likelihood of tokens being output. There are many ways in which we will improve the quality and value of the sheet music produced by the system, guided by the feedback from pianists described above. A major new direction will be to supplement constraint-led and model-led approaches with *content-led* ones. The constraint system will force certain notes at certain times, so given musical content can be reflected in the output. While useful for tasks like harmonisation exercises, melody generation over chords and producing expressive renderings, we plan to use it to generate longer, more structured piano pieces. This will be achieved by the system re-using and re-interpreting material such as melodic motifs that it has already produced. Our long term aim is to enable composers-as-constrainers from amateur to professional to generate inspirational music, and for the system to help add to musical culture (Colton and Banar, 2023).

Acknowledgements

This work has been funded in part by the UKRI via grant EP/S022694/1 (the AI and Music Centre for Doctoral Training). We would like to thank the anonymous reviewers for their helpful feedback.

References

- Acosta, M.; College, H. M.; Bukey, I.; and Tsai, T. J. 2022. An exploration of generating sheet music images. In *International Society for Music Information Retrieval Conference*.
- Anders, T., and Miranda, E. R. 2011. Constraint programming systems for modeling music theories and composition. *ACM Comput. Surv.* 43:30:1–30:38.
- Bernstein, A. 2024. Alberti bass technique for piano. <https://www.hoffmanacademy.com/blog/alberti-bass>.
- Beyer, T., and Dai, A. 2024. End-to-end piano performance-midi to score conversion with transformers. In *Proceedings of the 25th International Society for Music Information Retrieval Conference*.
- Bhuyan, B.; Ramdane-Cherif, A.; Tomar, R.; and Singh, T. 2024. Neuro-symbolic artificial intelligence: a survey. *Neural Computing and Applications* 36:12809–12844.
- Bradshaw, L., and Colton, S. 2025. Aria-midi: A dataset of piano midi files for symbolic music modeling. In *Proceedings of the Thirteenth International Conference on Learning Representations*.
- Broad, T.; Berns, S.; Colton, S.; and Grierson, M. 2021. Active divergence with generative deep learning - A survey and taxonomy. In *Proceedings of the 12th International Conference on Computational Creativity*.
- Colton, S., and Banar, B. 2023. Automatically adding to artistic cultures. In *Proceedings of the International Conference on Computational Intelligence in Music, Sound, Art and Design*.
- De Boom, C.; Van Laere, S.; Verbelen, T.; and Dhoedt, B. 2020. Rhythm, chord and melody generation for lead sheets using recurrent neural networks. In Cellier, P., and Driessens, K., eds., *Machine Learning and Knowledge Discovery in Databases*, 454–461. Cham: Springer International Publishing.
- Eigenfeldt, A., and Pasquier, P. 2010. Realtime generation of harmonic progressions using constrained markov selection. In *Proceedings of the 1st International Conference on Computational Creativity*.
- Foster, D. 2023. *Generative Deep Learning, 2nd Edition*. O’Reilly.
- Gan, Q.; Wang, S.; Wu, S.; and Zhu, J. 2025. Pianomotion10m: Dataset and benchmark for hand motion generation in piano performance.
- Hanon, C.-L. 1993. *Hanon: The Virtuoso Pianist in 60 Exercises*. Alfred Music.
- Hut, L., and Anderson, J. 1974. *Handbook of Musical Scales with Emphasis on the Keyboard*. Mountain Press Publishing Co.
- Lin, Y.; Dai, X.; and Kong, Q. 2024. Musicscore: A dataset for music score modeling and generation. *arXiv:2406.11462*.
- Liu, H.-M., and Yang, Y.-H. 2018. Lead sheet generation and arrangement by conditional generative adversarial network. In *2018 17th IEEE International Conference on Machine Learning and Applications (ICMLA)*, 722–727.
- Liu, L.; Kong, Q.; Morfi, V.; and Benetos, E. 2022. Performance midi-to-score conversion by neural beat tracking. In *Proceedings of the 23rd International Society for Music Information Retrieval Conference*.
- Liu, Y.; Li, H.; Cheng, Y.; Ray, S.; Huang, Y.; Zhang, Q.; Du, K.; Yao, J.; Lu, S.; Ananthanarayanan, G.; Maire, M.; Hoffmann, H.; Holtzman, A.; and Jiang, J. 2024. Cachegen: KV cache compression and streaming for fast large language model serving.
- Llano, M.; d’Inverno, M.; Yee-King, M.; McCormack, J.; Ilsar, A.; Pease, A.; and Colton, S. 2020. Explainable computational creativity. In *Proceedings of the 11th International Conference on Computational Creativity*.
- Long, P.; Novack, Z.; Berg-Kirkpatrick, T.; and McAuley, J. 2024. Pdmx: A large-scale public domain musicxml dataset for symbolic music processing. *arXiv:2409.10831*.
- Makris, D.; Agres, K. R.; and Herremans, D. 2021. Generating lead sheets with affect: A novel conditional seq2seq framework. In *2021 International Joint Conference on Neural Networks (IJCNN)*, 1–8.
- Micha. 2023. What is a soundfont? A comprehensive guide. *VIPZone* <https://www.vipzone-samples.com/en/what-is-a-soundfont/>.
- Nakamura, E.; Saito, Y.; and Yoshii, K. 2020. Statistical learning and estimation of piano fingering. *Information Sciences* 517:68–85.

- Pachet, F.; Papadopoulos, A.; and Roy, P. 2017. Sampling variations of sequences for structured music generation. In *International Society for Music Information Retrieval Conference*.
- Pachet, F.; Roy, P.; and Barbieri, G. 2011. Finite-length Markov processes with constraints. In *Proceedings of the Twenty-Second international joint conference on Artificial Intelligence*.
- Rossi, F.; van Beek, P.; and Walsh, T., eds. 2006. *Handbook of Constraint Programming*. Elsevier.
- Sakai, S.; Segawa, H.; and Kitahara, T. 2024. Tablature generation from lead sheets for finger-style solo guitar.
- Schiex, T. 1992. Possibilistic constraint satisfaction problems or “how to handle soft constraints?”. In Dubois, D.; Wellman, M. P.; D’Ambrosio, B.; and Smets, P., eds., *Uncertainty in Artificial Intelligence*. Morgan Kaufmann. 268–275.
- Sturm, B.; Santos, J.; and Korshunova, I. 2015. Folk music style modelling by recurrent neural networks with long short term memory units. In *Proceedings of the 16th International Society for Music Information Retrieval Conference (ISMIR)*.
- Valverde, R. 2025. How to project emotions through music: Choosing the right key. <https://blog.flat.io/choose-the-right-key/>.
- Vaswani, A.; Shazeer, N.; Parmar, N.; Uszkoreit, J.; Jones, L.; Gomez, A.; Kaiser, L.; and Polosukhin, I. 2017. Attention is all you need. *Proc. Advances in Neural Information Processing Systems* 30.
- Wang, Y.; Wu, S.; Hu, J.; Du, X.; Peng, Y.; Huang, Y.; Fan, S.; Li, X.; Yu, F.; and Sun, M. 2025. Notagen: Advancing musicality in symbolic music generation with large language model training paradigms. *arXiv:2502.18008*.
- Widmer, G., and Goebel, W. 2004. Computational models of expressive music performance: The state of the art. *Journal of New Music Research* 33(3):203–216.
- Yang, L.; Zhang, Z.; Song, Y.; Hong, S.; Xu, R.; Zhao, Y.; Zhang, W.; Cui, B.; and Yang, M. 2023. Diffusion models: A comprehensive survey of methods and applications. *ACM Computing Surveys* Volume 56(4).
- Zakka, K.; Wu, P.; Smith, L.; Gileadi, N.; Howell, T.; Peng, X.; Singh, S.; Tassa, Y.; Florence, P.; Zeng, A.; and Abbeel, P. 2023. Robopianist: Dexterous piano playing with deep reinforcement learning. In *Conference on Robot Learning (CoRL)*.

Appendix 1: Performance MIDI to Score Conversions

We used the piano transcription approach described in (Bradshaw and Colton, 2025) to produce a performance MIDI file of pianist Lang Lang's performance² of Für Elise (Bagatelle No. 25 in A minor (WoO 59, Bia 515)) by Beethoven. We then converted this to score with commercial packages GarageBand and MuseScore, then using the state of the art MIDI to MusicXML approach in (Beyer and Dai, 2024)³, followed by MuseScore to turn the MusicXML file into sheet music. The original score is given along with the three conversions below. While each conversion is a good start, unfortunately, none are up to the standard required for readable/playable piano music. Highlighting just a few issues, we see that GarageBand doesn't handle the rubato performance of the melody notes correctly, and introduces rests where there are none in the original sheet music. Only MuseScore correctly predicts that time signature of the original, but gets some onsets wrong, requiring notes held over bars, oddly provides four parts and gets the key signature wrong. The (Beyer and Dai, 2024) approach hasn't handled the usage of the sustain pedal correctly, with long bass notes in the left hand.

Original Sheet Music

The original sheet music for Für Elise is shown in a 3/8 time signature. The piano part begins with a *pp* dynamic marking. The melody is written in the right hand, and the bass line is in the left hand. The music features a mix of eighth and sixteenth notes, with some notes beamed together.

Conversion to Score with GarageBand

The conversion to score using GarageBand shows a 4/4 time signature. The melody is written in the right hand, and the bass line is in the left hand. The music features a mix of eighth and sixteenth notes, with some notes beamed together. The score includes several sustain pedal markings (*Ped.) in the bass line, which are not present in the original score.

Conversion to Score with MuseScore

The conversion to score using MuseScore shows a 3/8 time signature. The melody is written in the right hand, and the bass line is in the left hand. The music features a mix of eighth and sixteenth notes, with some notes beamed together. The score includes several notes held over bars, which are not present in the original score. The key signature is three sharps (F#, C#, G#), which is incorrect for Für Elise.

Conversion to MusicXML with Beyer and Dai (2024), then to Score with MuseScore

The conversion to score using MuseScore after MIDI to MusicXML conversion shows a 4/4 time signature. The melody is written in the right hand, and the bass line is in the left hand. The music features a mix of eighth and sixteenth notes, with some notes beamed together. The score includes several notes held over bars, which are not present in the original score. The key signature is three sharps (F#, C#, G#), which is incorrect for Für Elise.

²Video of the performance here: https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=s71l_EWJk7I

³Using the code from here: <https://github.com/TimFelixBeyer/MIDI2ScoreTransformer>

Appendix 2: Algorithm for the Application of Hard and Soft Onset Constraints

To describe an algorithm which uses both hard and soft constraints to add notes to an evolving piece of music, we introduce the definitions below. To employ the system, the user defines a constraint decision graph, G , (definition 9), where each node is a segment specification (def. 8). They do this by setting duration, pitch/volume (PV) and onset constraints (defs 2, 3 and 4), using these to specify note constraints (def. 6) with hard and soft onsets and compiling these into segment specifications. The nodes of G are traversed as the music changes, with movement along edges triggered by changes such as the completion of a certain bar, or a modulation.

Each segment specification constrains the choices for the addition of tokens (def. 1) for a certain number of beats. Algorithm 1 below sketches how onset constraints are partitioned (def. 7) in order to do this, with a PV, onset and duration token added sequentially, which together define a MIDI note. The constraints ensure that the nature and order of the notes fit the user requirements and can be mapped to a score in an appropriate manner. Algorithm 1 describes how to repeatedly set up a constraint satisfaction problem by reducing the options for tokens that can be generated. TTM then solves the problem by choosing between the alternatives using logit mackling. The approach works by determining which hard onset constraints need to be satisfied at the start of each partition of the segment, fulfilling those constraints, then moving on to soft constraints. A counter for each onset is reduced each time it is used, so that when the counter reaches zero, it can no longer be used.

Definition 1. A MIDI note, N , is represented by three *token* types output by TTM, namely a $\langle \text{piano}, P, V \rangle$ PV-token which represent the MIDI (P)itch and (V)olume of N , an $\langle \text{onset}, O \rangle$ token which represents the MIDI onset of N , and a $\langle \text{duration}, D \rangle$ token which represents the MIDI duration of N .

Definition 2. A *duration constraint* is a set of valid values that a duration token can take.

Definition 3. A *PV constraint* is a pair of (i) a set of valid pitches, and (ii) a set of valid volumes for a PV-token.

Definition 4. An *onset constraint* is a set of valid values for an onset token. These values are in a contiguous neighbourhood around a particular onset centre, denoted $oc(C)$ for onset constraint C . Each onset constraint has an associated beat, denoted $beat(C)$, which is relative the start of the segment that the note constraint (see below) is within.

Definition 5. A token, T , generated by TTM *satisfies* a constraint C if T is in the set of allowed values afforded by C . We say that a token is *generated* with a set of constraints if the logits produced by TTM are mackled to exclude all but the values in at least one of the constraints before sampling.

Definition 6. A *note constraint*, NC , consists of a quadruple $[PV, D, H, S]$, where PV is a PV constraint and D is a duration constraint. Here, $H = [h_0, \dots, h_x]$ denotes a list of *hard onset constraints* for NC , which is a set of pairs (C, N) where C is an onset constraint and N is an integer. The elements of H are ordered in increasing value of $onset(C)$. $S = [s_1, \dots, s_y]$ is likewise a set of such pairs, and denotes the *soft onset constraints* for NC . We write $hard(NC)$ for the hard onset constraints of NC and $soft(NC)$ for the soft onset constraints. Likewise, we use $pv(NC)$ for the PV constraint of NC and $dur(NC)$ for the duration constraint.

Definition 7. Given a note constraint, NC , if $hard(NC)$ is empty, then the *onset partitioning* of NC , denoted $opart(NC)$, is taken as $\{\{s \in soft(NC)\}\}$, otherwise it is the following list of sets ordered by onsets:

$$\begin{aligned} & \{\{s \in soft(NC) \text{ s.t. } oc(s) < h_1\}, \\ & \{h_1\} \cup \{s \in soft(NC) \text{ s.t. } h_1 \leq oc(s) < h_2\}, \\ & \quad \vdots \\ & \{h_x\} \cup \{s \in soft(NC) \text{ s.t. } h_x \leq oc(s)\} \end{aligned}$$

Given a set, p , in this partition, we denote:
 $mb(p) = \min(\{beat(c) : c \in p\})$.

Definition 8. A *segment specification* comprises a pair (N, B) where N is a set of note constraints, and B is an integer representing the number of beats of music the segment will be used to fill.

Definition 9. A *constraint decision graph* (CDG) is a connected graph with segment specifications as nodes, and edges that each have a condition attached. One of the segment specifications is singled out as a *starting node*.

Algorithm 1 Applying the constraints of a segment specification, Seg , to add MIDI notes to a sequence.

```

 $Seg = (N, B)$ 
 $ops = \{op : \exists NC \in N \text{ s.t. } op \in opart(NC)\}$ 
for  $b$  in  $(1, 1.25, \dots, B + 0.75)$  do
   $app = \{op \in ops : mb(op) = b\}$ 
   $NCs = \{NC \in N : \exists a \in app \text{ s.t. } a \in opart(NC)\}$ 
  if  $NCs \neq \emptyset$  then
     $PVC = \{pv(NC) : NC \in NCs\}$ 
    Generate  $PV$   $PV$ -token with  $PVC$  as constraints
     $PNC = \{NC \in NCs \text{ s.t. } PV \text{ satisfies } NC\}$ 
     $HN = \{(h, n) \in hard(NC) : NC \in PNCs\}$ 
     $H = \{h : (h, n) \in HN \wedge n > 0\}$ 
    if  $H \neq \emptyset$  then
      Generate  $O$  onset token with  $H$  as constraints
      if  $\exists (h, n) \in HN$  s.t.  $O$  satisfies  $h$  then
         $n \rightarrow n - 1$ 
      end if
    end if
  else
     $SN = \{(s, n) \in soft(NC) : NC \in PNCs\}$ 
     $S = \{s : (s, n) \in SN \wedge n > 0\}$ 
    if  $S \neq \emptyset$  then
       $F = overflow(max(\{onset(s) : s \in S\}))$ 
      Generate  $O$  onset token with  $S$  and  $F$ 
      if  $\exists (s, n) \in SN$  s.t.  $O$  satisfies  $s$  then
         $n \rightarrow n - 1$ 
      end if
    end if
  end if
  if  $O \in F$  then
    backtrack two tokens
  else
    Find  $NC \in N$  which is satisfied by  $PV$  and  $O$ 
    Generate  $D$  duration token with  $dur(NC)$ 
  end if
end if
   $bm$ 
end for

```

Appendix 3: Sample Constraint Decision Graphs (CDGs) and Outputs

Feelz Compositions

The composer's aim here was to produce melancholic music to be played with emotion. They used a global constraint forcing a D minor scale, as this is associated with melancholic music (Valverde, 2025). The CDG for these compositions used drift constraints for an initial crescendo from a piano or pianissimo start, and a rallentando passage at the end. It enforced a standard bass/chord accompaniment over a fixed, given chord sequence, and within-bar right hand passages where the intervals are no more than a fifth, producing somewhat voice-leading melodies.

Feelz Miniature #17

seed: 1740702657
date: 28/02/2025

Allegretto (♩ = 103)

The musical score for 'Feelz Miniature #17' is presented in a grand staff format (treble and bass clefs). The piece is in 4/4 time and D minor. It begins with a tempo marking of 'Allegretto' and a quarter note equal to 103 beats per minute. The score is divided into five systems, each with a measure number (1, 7, 10, 13, 16) at the start of the first staff. Dynamics include *pp*, *p*, *mp*, *mf*, and *dim. accel.*. Performance instructions include 'rall.' and 'dim. accel.'. The piece concludes with a final cadence in the bass staff.

Alberti Bass Compositions

The composer's aim here was to produce piano studies to practice Alberti Bass accompaniment (Bernstein, 2024) in the left hand and arpeggios in the right. Cluster constraints were used to force sequences of pitches in ranges, e.g., right-hand arpeggios had intervals of between three and five semitones. The system randomly chooses a scale for the notes to adhere to, and to add intrigue, a scale change is imposed halfway through, to the scale one semitone above. Sometimes the change was quite abrupt, but sometimes TTM managed to feather in a plausible modulation. The segment following the change allowed two-note chords in the right hand on the first and third beats, with no right hand arpeggio requirement, so TTM improvised here (although often continued with arpeggios).

Alberti Miniature #4

seed: 1740692738
date: 27/02/2025

Allegretto (♩ = 105)

The score is written for piano in 4/4 time, with a key signature of two flats (B-flat and E-flat). It consists of six systems of music, each with a treble and bass clef staff. The first system starts with a *mp* dynamic and includes a *mf* dynamic marking. The second system continues the piece. The third system features a scale change halfway through. The fourth system includes a *mp* dynamic marking. The fifth system includes a *mf* dynamic marking and a *rall.* (rallentando) instruction. The sixth system ends with a *mp* dynamic marking. The final system shows a simple chordal structure in the right hand and a single note in the left hand.

Freeform Compositions

The composer's aim here was to see what TTM produces in a relatively unconstrained way. The CDG contained only one segment which allowed zero to five notes in each hand on any quarter beat of every bar. The pitch, volume and duration constraints allowed all possible tokens. Hence TTM generated music in a mostly unconstrained way, with onset constraints used only to enable transcription to a score. As a result, while the music is highly diverse, the written form for these pieces can be difficult to follow, as TTM is not being constrained to follow a bar structure.

Freeform Miniature #29

seed: 1740707299
date: 28/02/2025

Moderato (♩ = 74)

The musical score for 'Freeform Miniature #29' is presented in a standard two-staff format (treble and bass clef) for piano. The tempo is marked 'Moderato' with a quarter note equal to 74 beats per minute. The key signature is one sharp (F#) and the time signature is 4/4. The score is divided into six systems, each containing two staves. The music is highly rhythmic and complex, with many notes per beat. Dynamics include *p*, *pp*, *mp*, and *p*. The piece ends with a final chord in the bass clef.